

Predicting Intra-City Mobility Flows without Using Historical Flow Data

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Abstract. This work in progress proposes a new deep learning-based method to generate intra-city mobility flows without using historical *flow* data. The proposed model takes the population/traveler volume of individual regions as inputs, and assumes no further geographical or mobility information about these regions, making it an effective and simple approach to be applied to many cities.

Keywords. Missing historical flow data, mobility flow, deep learning, prediction.

1. Introduction

Modelling human flows within cities is essential for city management, urban planning, and other mobility-related applications (e.g., infectious disease controlling, traffic optimization). Presently, state-of-the-art flow generation models, such as those relying on machine/deep learning (e.g., Graph Convolutional Network), require historical flow data for model fitting, and fail when such data are not available.

The generation or imputation of missing mobility flows between different regions is a major challenge in the study of human mobility. Initially, Zipf (1946) attempted to model the flows using a classic flow generation model, known as the gravity model $F_{i,j} = \frac{P_i P_j}{f(d)} = \frac{P_i P_j}{d^\beta}$, which assumes that the number of people $F_{i,j}$ moving between regions i and j is proportional to the population (or travelling volume; P_i and P_j) of the two regions, and decays with the distance d between them. To predict mobility flows, the gravity model requires an accurate estimation of the ‘distance’ between any two regions. However, there exists no effective method for estimating such distances.

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Many recent extensions to the gravity model have been proposed (Simini et al. 2012), by adding more parameters to the model, which however often requires massive historical flow data for parameter estimation. Therefore, they could not be applied in areas without historical *flow* data.

In short, there exists no effective method that can accurately generate or impute mobility flows in the absent of historical *flow* data. To address these existing gaps, we develop an adaptive gravity model based on deep learning and gradient descent to adaptively determine the deterrence function d , and further generate/impute mobility flow $F_{i,j}$ between any two regions i and j without using any historical flow data. The model relies only on the volume of travelers (or population; P_i and P_j) of each region over time.

2. Methodology

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed adaptive gravity model. Suppose that $X_t \in \mathbf{R}^{N \times 1}$ represents the traveler volume at the given time step t , where N denotes the total number of regions. Depending on the type of mobility data, a region can be a regular grid cell, a traffic analysis zone (TAZ) or a census tract. $X_t[i]$ is the traveler volume of region i at time t .

The training task can be then defined as follows: Given observations of N regions at time t ($X_t \in \mathbf{R}^{N \times 1}$), the adaptive gravity model aims to train the deterrence function $f(d)$ by predicting the traveler volume of N regions at time $t+1$, $Y = \hat{X}_{t+1} \in \mathbf{R}^{N \times 1}$. However, predicting the traveler volume at $t+1$ is not our target, our goal is to obtain the deterrence function $f(d)$ by this training task, and then apply the trained $f(d)$ to generate mobility flows between any two regions.

$$\hat{X}_{t+1}[i] = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{X_t X_t^T}{f(d)} [j, i] \right) \quad (1)$$

$$f(d) = d^\beta \quad (2)$$

Where $\hat{X}_{t+1}[i] \in \mathbf{R}^{1 \times 1}$ is traveler volume of region i at time $t+1$, which is calculated by summing all elements of the i th column of the matrix $\frac{X_t X_t^T}{f(d)}$. $f(d) \in \mathbf{R}^{N \times N}$ (green matrix in Figure 1) is a trainable deterrence function with the initial value as the actual geographical distances (i.e., d_o is the Euclidean distance of the center points of the regions). Its values will be changed after training to obtain a better deterrence function.

After training, the deterrence function $f(d)$ can be determined. We can then use the form of the gravity model to generate mobility flow $F_t \in \mathbf{R}^{N \times N}$ between any two regions at time t :

$$V_t = \frac{X_t X_t^T}{f(d)} \quad (3)$$

$$F_t[i, j] = \frac{V_{i,j}}{\sum_{m,n} V_{m,n}} \sum_{k=1}^N X_t[k] \quad (4)$$

Where $V \in \mathbf{R}^{N \times N}$ (grey matrix in Figure 1) is a set of intermediate values that are associated with the actual flows. $X_t = [X_t[1], \dots, X_t[n], \dots, X_t[N]]$ represents the traveler volume of each region at time t , $F_t[i, j]$ represents the generated flow from region i to region j .

This model can be trained by minimizing the mean absolute error (MAE) loss function between the predicted traveler volume and the actual traveler volume in each region.

$$loss = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\hat{X}_{t+1}[i] - X_{t+1}[i]| \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. Architecture of the proposed adaptive gravity model. The traveler volume of each region at time t concatenates the input X_t to be fed into the model separately over time series. d is a trainable distance-based matrix with initial value d_0 . The output F_t denotes the generated flows between any two regions at time t . In other words, predicting the traveler volume X_{t+1} at $t+1$ is not our final aim, our goal is to obtain the trained deterrence function $f(d)$ (the green matrix), and then apply the trained $f(d)$ to generate mobility flows F_t between any two regions.

Note that the proposed model only takes the traveler volume of individual regions as inputs, and does not use any mobility flow data between regions. It overcomes two limitations of the basic gravity model: the difficulty of obtaining a suitable distance function, and the inability of generating directed flows between regions.

3. Evaluation: work in progress

Currently, we are evaluating the proposed model using data from five cities: Chicago, New York, Nanjing, Porto, and Los Angeles, covering different countries, continents, different city sizes, different dataset types (ride-hailing data vs. mobile phone data), and different spatial partitioning (regular grids, TAZs, census tracts).

The first evaluation results show that the proposed model consistently and significantly outperforms state-of-the-art baselines across all the datasets and time intervals. The full evaluation results will be available in the coming months.

References

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